

Determinants of Debt Tax Shield of non-Financial Firms in Nigeria

¹OMOGOR, Franca; and ²JEROH, Edirin;

^{1, & 2} Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Science, Delta State University, Abraka - Nigeria.

Abstract

This study investigated the determinants of tax shields among non-financial firms in Nigeria using panel data covering 11 listed firms from 2013 to 2023, yielding 121 firm-year observations. Focusing on the debt tax shield as the core dependent variable, the study incorporates profitability and firm-specific characteristics as explanatory factors. Unit root tests using the Phillips–Perron Fisher panel procedure indicate stationarity at level for debt tax shield alongside the selected variables measuring firm characteristics. The Pedroni cointegration test, particularly the Phillips–Perron group statistic, confirms the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables. Results from pooled OLS, fixed-effects, and random-effects models are consistent with theoretical expectations, with firm size exerting a statistically significant positive effect on the debt tax shield under both pooled OLS and random-effects estimations. Robustness diagnostics including variance inflation factor, heteroscedasticity tests, and the Hausman specification test validate the reliability of the findings. Granger causality results further show a bi-directional relationship running from firm size to the debt tax shield. The study recommends among others that managers should carefully assess the optimal level of debt in relation to firm size and operational capacity to maximize tax benefits without overexposing the firm to financial risk

1.0 Introduction

Tax shield refers to the reduction in taxable income that an individual or firm can achieve through allowable deductions, either by deferring tax payments or lowering taxable income within a given period (Okocha & Jeroh, 2024). The effectiveness of tax shields is influenced by several factors, including a firm's capital structure, profitability, and the regulatory environment (Oyedokun, Akintoye, & Salawu, 2018; Okonkwo, 2018; Iyefekhe & Imagbe, 2019). Modigliani and Miller (1963) highlighted the role of debt in capital structure, emphasizing that the interest tax deduction associated with debt can enhance firm value. However, excessive debt introduces financial risk and the potential for distress or bankruptcy if firms fail to balance tax benefits with associated costs (Graham, 2000).

Firms with higher profitability, larger asset bases, and established operational histories are more likely to exploit debt tax shields to maximize value (Okonkwo et al., 2023; Oyedokun, & Ayinde, 2023). In the Nigerian context, tax administration remains largely ineffective, and many firms engage in tax avoidance strategies to reduce costs. Substituting debt for tax avoidance can benefit firms if the cost of debt is lower, as interest expenses reduce taxable income and generate a tax saving or “shield”. Nevertheless, excessive leverage increases financial risk, requiring firms to carefully balance the benefits of debt with potential costs.

Debt utilization, particularly in relation to equity or asset base, can signal efficient resource management to investors, enhancing market confidence, dividend potential, and share prices. Profitability and sustained operations further strengthen investor confidence, improve market

capitalization, and provide firms with resources for growth (Abdulmumin, 2020; Oyedokun, & Onigbinde, 2024). Although numerous studies have examined determinants of tax shields in corporate entities, few have incorporated key variants of profitability and firm characteristics when analyzing the debt tax shield among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Accordingly, this study seeks to investigate the influence of debt tax shields on the value of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Debt Tax Shield

The debt tax shield represents the reduction in a firm's taxable income resulting from the deductibility of interest expenses on borrowed funds used to finance its operations (Oyedokun, Fowokan, Akintoye, & Dada, 2018; Okocha & Jeroh, 2024). In essence, the debt tax shield reflects the tax-saving effect arising from the pre-tax deduction of corporate interest expenses, which reduces the overall tax liability of the firm. According to Modigliani and Miller (1963), firms that rely more heavily on debt within their capital structure can enhance their value by leveraging this tax advantage, as interest payments on debt are allowable deductions from taxable income. By lowering taxable income, firms effectively reduce the amount of tax owed, thereby creating a "shield" that preserves cash flows for reinvestment or distribution to shareholders.

The magnitude of the debt tax shield depends on the level of debt employed relative to the firm's total capital and the prevailing corporate tax rate. Firms that strategically utilize external financing in place of equity financing can gain significant financial benefits, including increased after-tax cash flows, enhanced firm value, and potential advantages such as tax holidays or deferred tax obligations, compared to relying solely on dividends for shareholder returns (Oyedokun, & Sorinmade, 2023; Okocha & Jeroh, 2024). Prudently managing the balance between debt and equity not only maximizes the tax shield but also contributes to the firm's overall financial efficiency, supporting investment, growth, and sustainable shareholder value.

2.2 Determinants of Debt Tax Shield

The debt tax shield is influenced by multiple factors, with profitability and firm-specific characteristics being among the most critical determinants. Understanding these factors is essential for explaining how firms optimize the benefits of debt financing and enhance their overall value.

2.2.1 Profitability

Profitability is a key determinant of a firm's capacity to exploit debt tax shields, as it reflects the firm's ability to generate earnings from its resources while sustaining long-term financial health (Wang & Wang, 2022). Firms with higher profitability are better positioned to utilize debt effectively because they can service interest payments and reduce taxable income without compromising operational stability. Commonly used profitability metrics include Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Tobin's Q, which provide insight into operational efficiency, shareholder value, and market valuation, respectively.

2.2.2 Return on Assets (ROA)

ROA measures how efficiently a firm converts its assets into net income. A higher ROA indicates effective asset utilization and operational performance, which can support a firm's ability to service debt and maximize the benefits of tax-deductible interest expenses. ROA is therefore positively associated with both firm value and the effective use of debt tax shields.

2.2.3 Return on Equity (ROE)

ROE evaluates the profitability generated relative to shareholders' equity, highlighting the efficiency with which a firm uses invested capital to generate returns. Firms with higher ROE can sustain debt obligations more reliably, enhancing their capacity to leverage the debt tax shield while maintaining investor confidence (Okafor & Ezeani, 2023).

2.2.4 Tobin's Q,

Tobin's Q which compares a firm's market value to the replacement cost of its assets, provides an indication of market perceptions of firm value relative to its tangible and intangible resources. Higher Tobin's Q values suggest that markets recognize the growth potential and value creation capacity of the firm, which can influence management decisions on debt financing and tax planning strategies, particularly in sectors where intangible assets play a central role (Ayuba & Suleiman, 2021).

2.2.5 Firm Size

This is a critical determinant of financial strategy, as larger firms typically have greater access to capital markets, higher borrowing capacity, and enhanced credibility with lenders (Al-Slehat, 2019). Large firms are therefore better positioned to implement effective debt-financing strategies, benefiting from the associated tax deductions while maintaining operational stability. In the Nigerian context, firm size is particularly relevant in capital-intensive sectors, where substantial debt financing is often required for expansion and investment (Ajube & Jeroh, 2023).

2.2.6 Firm Age

This is closely associated with financial credibility and reduced perceived risk. Older firms often enjoy easier access to financing, favorable credit terms, and established operational frameworks that enable them to manage debt more efficiently (Okonkwo, 2018). As a result, mature firms in Nigeria are generally more capable of leveraging debt tax shields to enhance financial performance and ensure long-term sustainability (Ogbeide et al., 2022).

Collectively, profitability and firm-specific characteristics shape a firm's capacity to utilize debt as a strategic tool for tax planning and value creation. By aligning these factors with appropriate capital structure decisions, firms can optimize tax savings, strengthen financial resilience, and enhance shareholder wealth.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 Pecking Order Theory

The Pecking Order Theory (POT) provides a behavioral framework for understanding firms' financing preferences. The theory posits that firms prioritize internal financing (retained earnings) over external financing, and when external funds are needed, debt is preferred over

equity. This preference hierarchy arises because debt is generally considered less costly and less risky compared to issuing new equity, which may signal overvaluation to investors and dilute existing ownership. Proponents of the POT further notes that the use of debt can convey confidence to the market, signaling that management expects stable future cash flows and sufficient profitability to service obligations.

The relevance of the Pecking Order Theory to the current study is particularly significant. In the context of Nigerian non-financial firms, firms often face constraints in accessing external equity due to market inefficiencies, regulatory challenges, and high transaction costs. As such, firms are likely to rely on debt financing to fund operations and investments. This reliance on debt has direct implications for the debt tax shield, as interest payments on debt are tax-deductible and reduce taxable income, thereby generating tangible tax savings. By applying POT, this study can explain the observed financing behavior of Nigerian firms and how such behavior affects their ability to exploit debt tax shields.

Moreover, the theory provides a foundation for analyzing how firm-specific factors such as profitability, size, and age influence debt financing decisions. For instance, highly profitable firms may prefer internal financing and resort to debt only when retained earnings are insufficient, whereas younger or smaller firms with limited internal funds may rely more heavily on debt. In both cases, debt utilization directly contributes to the firm's capacity to reduce tax liabilities through the debt tax shield mechanism. Therefore, POT not only explains the financing hierarchy but also underpins the determinants of debt tax shields by linking firm behaviour, financing choices, and tax efficiency.

2.5 Empirical Review

Okocha and Jeroh (2024) examined the impact of debt and non-debt tax shields on the value of 62 publicly listed Nigerian firms from 2012 to 2021, using Tobin's Q as a proxy for firm value. Secondary data from financial statements were analyzed through robust regression, supported by descriptive and diagnostic tests. The study found that debt tax shields did not significantly influence firm value, indicating limited market impact from using debt to reduce taxable income. In contrast, non-debt tax shields, such as depreciation and investment-related deductions, were positively and significantly associated with higher firm valuations. The findings suggest that while debt financing can support capital projects, its effect on market value is constrained. The study recommends that firms strategically leverage non-debt tax shields to enhance profitability and growth, and urges policymakers to expand tax incentives to strengthen the operating environment for Nigerian firms.

Adekunle and Afolabi (2023) investigated how profitability impacts tax shield utilization, using a sample of highly profitable Nigerian manufacturing firms. They found that firms with higher profit margins are better positioned to benefit from debt-related tax shields, as they have greater taxable income to offset. The authors recommended that profitable firms adopt leveraged financing to maximize tax savings.

Babalola and Ibrahim (2023) analyzed firm size's role in tax shield utilization in Nigeria, using a regression analysis on a sample of large firms listed on the NSE. Their results showed that larger firms were more likely to use tax shields effectively due to better access to credit and increased leverage opportunities. They recommended that small firms explore credit options to improve their tax planning.

Musa and Olowolayemo (2023) extended this analysis by examining share price volatility and its impact on tax planning. They used GARCH models to analyze the relationship between share price volatility and tax shield strategies in Nigerian firms. Their findings indicated that firms with stable or rising share prices tend to pursue tax-efficient strategies more aggressively than those with volatile prices. This study recommended that companies work on stabilizing their market performance to optimize tax benefits, especially for long-term tax shield strategies.

Okoye and IHEMEJE (2023) studied industry-specific factors affecting tax shields in Nigeria's manufacturing and services sectors. They employed a comparative analysis, using regression models to examine industry-specific variables such as capital intensity and debt levels. Their findings revealed that manufacturing firms with significant physical capital assets were better positioned to benefit from depreciation-related tax shields than service-oriented firms. They concluded that firms should consider industry characteristics when planning tax-efficient strategies and recommended that the Nigerian government offer industry-specific tax incentives.

Amadi and Chijioke (2023) examined the impact of firm age on tax shield benefits in Nigerian SMEs. Their regression analysis showed that older SMEs, due to accumulated assets and established credit profiles, were better positioned to benefit from tax shields through debt financing. These older firms, with their higher creditworthiness, could more effectively use interest deductions to reduce taxable income. The study concluded that firm age contributes positively to tax shield benefits and encouraged younger SMEs to build creditworthiness as a strategy to access similar tax advantages over time.

Eniola et al. (2023) conducted a longitudinal study examining the role of firm age in tax shield strategies among Nigerian non-financial firms. Their research used a fixed-effects model to analyze firm age and its impact on tax shields, finding that older firms generally have more substantial debt-related tax shields due to established lender relationships. The study recommended that younger firms work to build creditworthiness to access greater tax shield benefits.

Musa and Ogunbiyi (2023) conducted a study on the interplay between capital structure and tax shields in Nigerian firms. Using a panel data analysis, they observed that firms with high debt levels benefitted significantly from tax-deductible interest payments, enhancing tax shield utilization. They recommended that companies consider the tax implications of their capital structure decisions to optimize tax efficiency.

Ogunbiyi and Femi (2023) explored how firm size influences tax shield efficiency in Nigeria's agricultural sector. Through a time-series analysis of agricultural firms over ten years, they observed that larger firms gained more tax shield benefits due to economies of scale and greater debt capacity. Larger agricultural firms, by having access to more significant credit facilities, could more effectively use interest deductions on debt to lower their tax burden. The study concluded that firm size is a vital determinant of tax shield utilization and advised smaller firms to pursue growth strategies that would enable them to access similar tax benefits.

Eke and Nwokolo (2023) assessed how economic policy changes impact tax shields in Nigeria's energy sector. Through a mixed-method approach involving quantitative analysis and interviews with financial managers, they found that frequent tax policy changes in Nigeria made it challenging for energy firms to develop consistent tax shield strategies. Particularly in a heavily regulated sector like energy, stable tax policies were seen as essential for predictable tax planning. The study concluded that policy stability enhances tax shield utilization in

regulated industries, and recommended that policymakers consider long-term tax regulations to facilitate more consistent financial planning within the energy sector.

Samuel, Akpan, Nsentip and Ukpe (2023) explored the impact of tax shields on the value of selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021, using Tobin's Q as a measure of firm value. The independent variables examined were debt tax shield, depreciation tax shield, and charitable donation tax shield. Utilizing an ex post facto research design and secondary data, the study applied ordinary least squares regression analysis with SPSS Version 20 to test three hypotheses. The results revealed that all three types of tax shields significantly influence the market value of these firms. Consequently, the study concluded that tax shields can be strategically used to enhance firm value in the Nigerian manufacturing sector. It recommended that management should consider increasing debt financing, investing in non-current assets, leveraging charitable donations to improve corporate image, and maintaining an optimal mix of tax shields to benefit shareholders and attract investors.

Ajube and Jeroh (2023) investigated determinants of tax aggressiveness among Nigerian listed non-financial firms using an ex-post facto design and secondary data from 2011–2020, sourced from the MachameRatios Positive Accounting Database. Regression analysis and diagnostic tests were employed. Results indicate that Return on Assets (ROA) and audit committee gender diversity do not significantly influence tax aggressiveness, whereas real earnings management and board independence have a significant impact. The study concludes that board independence and real earnings management are key drivers of tax aggressiveness in these firms. It recommends that the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria and other regulators enforce corporate governance codes requiring independent directors on boards and monitor corporate activities to curb tax aggressiveness, particularly through manipulation of real earnings.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study aims to approach a panel econometrics for the cross-sectional data among the two category of firms drawn from the six industries. This data will be obtained from secondary sources, specifically the published annual financial statements of accounts of the sampled companies which are level non-financial firms(11) because of the common features of the firms The set of data to be collected from these published annual financial statements are validated by the NGX and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), both of which regulate accounting and business operations in Nigeria.

3.1 Model Specification

$$Y_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j X_{jit} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where:

Y_{it} : represent dependent variable of interest.

i: individual unit of observation,

t: time period, capturing time effects.

j: observed explanatory variables as j ranges from 1 to n.

X: independent variables of interest.

μ_{it} : error term

Model I

$$DTAXS = (\text{Profitability, Firm's characteristics}) \quad (1).$$

The Model 1 equation can be transformed into econometric explicit forms as follows:

$$Dtax_{sit} = \alpha + \beta_1 (ROA_{it}) + \beta_2 ROE_{it} + \beta_3 FIRM_AGE_{it} + \beta_4 FIRM_SIZE_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

α = the intercept term or constant variable in each of the models.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 = slope coefficient or parameter of the independent variables respectively.

μ_{it} = the error term of the equation (Disturbance term).

i: individual unit of observation representing the selected listed non-financial firms for the purpose of this study,

t: time period, which allows for a shift of the intercept over time, capturing time effects.

Table 1 Measurement of Variables

Dependent variable	Variable code	Measurement	a priori expectation
Debt-tax shield	DTAXS	Tax shield measured by effective tax rate	+
Independent variables			
Profitability			
Return on asset	ROA	Net income to total asset	+
Return on equity	ROE	Net income to total equity	+
Tobin_q	TOBIN_Q	Firm value or Tobin's Q in number is computed as market capitalization + total liabilities - cash flow divided by total asset.	+
Firm characteristics			
Firm age	FIRM_AGE	Number of years of the reporting entity based on the date listed on NSE	+
Firm size	FIRM_SIZE	Measured by the log of total asset of the firm in a given year	+

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Preliminary Tests

Prior to presenting the major regression outcome, some relevant tests were conducted and this section presents the attendant outcomes.

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

Staistics	DTAXS	ROA	ROE	TOBIN_Q	FIRM_AG E	LN FIRM_ S IZE
Mean	0.337976	0.108501	0.229357	0.479655	35.76471	17.14072
Median	0.297100	0.073600	0.128300	0.519100	40.00000	16.67460
Maximum	2.448900	0.874600	1.950000	0.989300	53.00000	20.49678
Minimum	0.015000	0.002000	0.001100	0.033400	5.000000	14.17462
Std. Dev.	0.319419	0.129076	0.310804	0.209204	13.36115	1.799490
Skewness	3.798707	3.163236	3.576639	-0.213616	-1.173636	0.336598
Kurtosis	21.51621	15.09847	17.86008	2.941194	3.054499	1.800321
Jarque-Bera	1986.164	924.2201	1348.623	0.922177	27.33361	9.383260
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.630597	0.000001	0.009172
Sum	40.21910	12.91160	27.29350	57.07900	4256.000	2039.745
Sum Sq. Dev.	12.03938	1.965939	11.39869	5.164449	21065.41	382.1035
Observation s	119	119	119	119	119	119

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

As indicated in Table 2, the weighted average of debt-tax shield(DTAXS) shows that the mean value for the eleven(11) selected firms whose activities are related to manufacturing is (0.33) with maximum value of 2.4489 and minimum value of 0.0150. The independent variables measuring profitability have lower mean value respectively as 0.1085 and 0.2293 respectively for ROA and ROE while there is an indication of higher mean value for TOBIN_Q , firm age and firm size are 0.4796, 35.76471 and 17.1407 respectively. This is an evidence that ROA and ROE are unable to shield tax for better performance for the sampled firms while the firm age, firm size and TOBIN_Q with higher mean value are able to shield tax for better performance for the sampled firms. There is fair dispersion between the mean and standard deviation of, ROA, ROE and DTAXS with standard deviation of 0.12, 0.31 and 0.31 respectively while wide dispersion exist for firm age and firm size a estimated at 13.36. and 1.79 respectively.

4.1.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 3: Correlation Result

Variables	DTAXS	ROA	ROE	TOBIN_Q	FIRM_AG E	LN FIRM_ S IZE
DTAXS	1.000000					
ROA	-0.095391	1.000000				
ROE	-0.167600	0.388334	1.000000			
TOBIN_Q	0.116391	0.018902	0.232662	1.000000		
FIRM_AG E	-0.016867	0.001989	-0.099150	-0.060592	1.000000	-
LN FIRM_ S IZE	0.212880	-0.072433	-0.072747	-0.022199	-0.189281	1.000000

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

From the table result above, there is absence of strong correlation between debt-tax shield and the independent variables respectively. Debt-tax shield has negative relation with ROA(-0.09), ROE(-0.16) and firm age (0.016) while debt-tax shield has positive relation with TOBIN_Q(0.116) and firm size (-0.2128) hence this study confirm the absence of the problem of multicollinearity among the determinants of debt-tax shield for the sampled firms.

4.1.3 Unit Root Test

Table 4 Summary of Unit Root Test

Unit Root Test	Level					
	DTAXS	ROA	ROE	TOBIN-Q	FIRMAGE	FIRMSIZE
PP-fisher Statistic	69.6903	80.2720	79.7124	83.6808	96.8538	88.3890
Probability	(0.0000)	(0.0000)	(0.0000)	(0.0000)	(0.0000)	(0.0000)
Order of integration	I(0)	I(0)	I(0)	I(0)	I(0)	I(0)

Source: Author's Computation using Eviews Software

The result for Philip perron(PP-Fisher) unit root in the table above shows DTAXS, ROA, ROE, TOBIN_Q, FIRM_AGE and FIRM_SIZE as the adopted variables, at level, are found to be stationary at probability value (0.0000) with at least 1percent significant level. This the statistical properties (Mean, variance, autocorrelation) of the time series data are constant, implying that the variables are stationary in their level form. This further implies that a long run relationship exist among the selected variables. This therefore leads to testing for the long run relationship among the variables which have both economic and statistical implications. The economic implication of stationarity is that shocks to the variables will die off in the long run. The statistical implication of stationary is that there is likelihood of the Ordinary Least Squares estimator producing unbiased and consistent results.

4.1.4 Panel cointegration Test

Table 5 Summary of Cointegration

	Statistic		Weighted	
	Statistic	Prob.	Statistic	Prob.
Panel v-Statistic	-2.787230	0.9973	-2.823716	0.9976
Panel rho-Statistic	4.107374	1.0000	3.634033	0.9999
Panel PP-Statistic	0.072535	0.5289	-3.274751	0.0005
Panel ADF-Statistic	1.772729	0.9619	-0.235043	0.4071

Alternative hypothesis: individual AR coefs. (between-dimension)

	Statistic	Prob.
Group rho-Statistic	4.833381	1.0000
Group PP-Statistic	-3.553403	0.0002
Group ADF-Statistic	0.831267	0.7971

The results from the Pedroni cointegration test is to confirm the assumption of common autoregressive coefficients in order to provide any support for the existence of cointegration among the variables. The results show an evidence of cointegration among the variables as depicted by the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration at least 1% level of significance. The Philip perron (PP) Group statistic with probability of (0.0000) confirm the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration at 1% level of significance. In conclusion, there exist a long run relationship between debt-tax shield(DTAXS) and profitability using the measurement of Tobin_q, return on asset and return on equity and and also for firm characteristics using firm age and firm size.

4.1.5 Diagnostic Test

The tests carried out are multicollinearity and heteroskedasticity tests on the OLS result and Hausman specification test to select the best model between fixed and random effects models.

Table 6 Summary of Post Regression Test

Variable	Multicollinearity(VIF)	Heteroscedasticity	Hausman Test
ROA	1.190275	Observed R- square:7.62 Probability Chi- square: 0.1664	Hausman statistic:4.0596 Chi- square Probability: 0.5409
ROE	1.269677		
TOBIN_Q	1.064324		
FIRM AGE	1.053518		
FIRM_SIZE	1.048258		

Gujarati and Porter (2009) emphasized the case of no problem of multicollinearity if the VIF is less than 10. From the result above, the variance inflation factor (VIF) shows the estimate of less than 10.0 for each independent variable. The heteroscedasticity result shows Chi-square probability values for model 1(0.1664) is greater than 5 percent and acceptable to be statistically significant for null hypothesis. This implies the absence of heteroskedasticity, that is, there is constant variance among the residuals of the models. The Hausman chi-square statistic (4.0596) with Probability (0.5409) greater than 5 percent implies the random estimate is preferred to fixed effect estimate.

4.2 Hypothesis Test and Discussion

Based on the previous subsections, the regression result is as follow:

Table 7 Summarized Panel Linear Regression Results
Dependent variable=debt tax shield(DTAXS)

Variable	Pooled OLS Effect		Fixed Effect		Random Effect	
	Coefficient	Probability	Coefficient	Probability	Coefficient	Probability
ROA	-0.029180	0.9041	-0.220434	0.4193	-0.370760	0.2485
ROE	-0.190317	0.0690	-0.169962	0.1509	-0.029180	0.9046
TOBIN_Q	0.252028	0.0767	0.291778	0.0809	-0.190317	0.0706
FIRM AGE	0.000324	0.8829	-0.000805	0.9132	0.252028	0.0784
FIRM SIZE	0.036350	0.0274	0.013397	0.7379	0.000324	0.8836
C	-- 0.3707	0.2457	0.060068	0.9301	0.036350	0.0283
R ² = 0.05905 F-stat = 1.102675 D.W stat = 1.8852			R ² = 0.4204 F-stat = 4.9814 D.W stat = 1.82		R ² = 0.1077 F-stat = 2.7284 D.W stat = 1.92	

Source: Author's Computation using Eviews Software

The Panel Ordinary Least Square regression model is employed with the outcomes of estimation as given in the table above. The result of the factors influencing debt-tax shield (DTAXS) analysis from the eleven (11) non-financial institutions, mainly manufacturing firms in different capacity as well, shows that the coefficients of the variables of interest are in conformity with the a priori expectations. For instance, the result of the panel(common) OLS, panel fixed-effect and panel random-effect shows ROA negatively affect debt-tax shield with about (-0.029) ROE shows negative effect on debt-tax shield with about (-0.1903). The positive market value with positive TOBIN_Q improves the tax-shield with about (0.2520). Firm age positively affects tax- shield at the magnitude of 0.036 while firm size positively affect tax shield with a magnitude of 0.036. In relation to the influence of the explanatory variables on tax shield, only firm size statistically indicate significant relation with debt-tax shield from the regression component of the pooled OLS whereas, the fixed effect and the random effect components shows no statistically significant relation between any of the independent variables and the dependent variable. The R-square (0.05) estimate of the pool OLS component indicates weak explanation of the behavior of tax shield by the independent variables of less than 10 percent while for the random effect, R-square shows a change of (0.1011) above 10 percent for the explanation of the behavior of debt –tax shield by the influence of profitability and firm characteristics using ROA,ROE, TOBIN+ _Q ,FIRM_AGE and FIRM_SIZE. The fixed effect component shows the R-squared component shows a change of (0.4205) above 40 percent for the explanation of debt-tax shield behavior by the explanatory variables . All the components regression shows Durbin-Watson(DW) test approaches 2 which is appropriate to indicate absence of serial correlation among the explanatory variables.

4.3 Causality Estimate

Table 8 Granger Causality Result

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Date: 04/18/25 Time: 03:27			
Sample: 2013 2023			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
ROA does not Granger Cause DTAXS	94	0.81252	0.4470
DTAXS does not Granger Cause ROA		0.34377	0.7100
ROE does not Granger Cause DTAXS	94	0.31705	0.7291
DTAXS does not Granger Cause ROE		0.52633	0.5926
TOBIN_Q does not Granger Cause DTAXS	94	0.02767	0.9727
DTAXS does not Granger Cause TOBIN_Q		0.03095	0.9695
FIRM_AGE does not Granger Cause DTAXS	94	0.00694	0.9931
DTAXS does not Granger Cause FIRM_AGE		30.1265	1.E-10
FIRM_SIZE does not Granger Cause DTAXS	94	4.07832	0.0202
DTAXS does not Granger Cause FIRM_SIZE		33.0026	2.E-11
ROE does not Granger Cause ROA	97	4.04708	0.0207
ROA does not Granger Cause ROE		0.69975	0.4993
TOBIN_Q does not Granger Cause ROA	97	0.50126	0.6074
ROA does not Granger Cause TOBIN_Q		0.00368	0.9963
FIRM_AGE does not Granger Cause ROA	97	0.16880	0.8449
ROA does not Granger Cause FIRM_AGE		689.309	4.E-56
FIRM_SIZE does not Granger Cause ROA	97	0.32099	0.7262
ROA does not Granger Cause FIRM_SIZE		0.01039	0.9897
TOBIN_Q does not Granger Cause ROE	97	2.29972	0.1060
ROE does not Granger Cause TOBIN_Q		3.04544	0.0524
FIRM_AGE does not Granger Cause ROE	97	3.31354	0.0408
ROE does not Granger Cause FIRM_AGE		1029.95	1.E-63
FIRM_SIZE does not Granger Cause ROE	97	0.42939	0.6522
ROE does not Granger Cause FIRM_SIZE		0.10469	0.9007
FIRM_AGE does not Granger Cause TOBIN_Q	97	0.20720	0.8132
TOBIN_Q does not Granger Cause FIRM_AGE		51.0982	1.E-15
FIRM_SIZE does not Granger Cause TOBIN_Q	97	0.36751	0.6935
TOBIN_Q does not Granger Cause FIRM_SIZE		2.05627	0.1338

FIRM_SIZE does not Granger Cause			
FIRM_AGE	97	-12.2301	1.0000
FIRM_AGE does not Granger Cause FIRM_SIZE		1.98144	0.1437

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Based on the selected determinants of debt tax shield, the causal results reveal uni-directional causality runs from firm size to debt-tax shield with the probability value (0.0202) and non-causality from debt-tax shield to firm size. The implication is that manufacturing firms with large assets can attract credit and enjoy more leverage in with the findings by Babalola & Ibrahim (2023). Profit before tax with adjustment for all income expenses such as deductions for debt servicing and other related expenses tied to manufacturing expenses reduces charges on tax amount for the firms at 5 percent significant level.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Debt serves as a critical resource for firms with long-term growth ambitions and simultaneously functions as an effective mechanism for tax mitigation. By maintaining an optimal capital structure that incorporates debt, firms can leverage the tax-deductibility of interest payments, thereby reducing taxable income and enhancing overall tax efficiency. The study findings reveal that higher levels of debt translate into greater tax savings, highlighting the strategic importance of debt management in firm financial planning. Moreover, debt levels can serve as an indicator of firm size, particularly for established firms with a longer operational history. Over time, performance metrics such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) provide insights into the operational and equity benefits derived from firm activities, reflecting the firm's capacity to sustain debt and exploit associated tax advantages.

Empirical analysis from this study, based on panel regression of sampled listed non-financial firms in Nigeria, indicates that firm size and firm age are significant determinants of the debt tax shield. Larger and more mature firms are better positioned to utilize contracted debt to complement operational capacity while maximizing tax savings. These findings suggest that strategic debt management should be considered a key component of financial policy for Nigerian non-financial firms.

Based on these findings, the study makes the following recommendations:

- i. Managers should carefully assess the optimal level of debt in relation to firm size and operational capacity to maximize tax benefits without overexposing the firm to financial risk.
- ii. Firms, particularly younger or smaller entities, should consider gradually increasing debt in a controlled manner to leverage tax advantages while maintaining solvency and financial stability.
- iii. Regular evaluation of firm performance through ROA, ROE, and other profitability metrics should guide decisions on debt utilization to ensure that borrowing aligns with operational efficiency and shareholder value creation.

- iv. Firms must ensure that debt-financing strategies comply with tax regulations and incorporate robust risk management practices to mitigate potential financial distress from excessive leverage.

References

- Abdulumumin, B.A. (2020). Determinants of debt financing in Nigeria. *EuroEconomica*, 3(39), 141-149.
- Adekunle, S., & Afolabi, D. (2023). Profitability and its impact on tax shields in Nigerian manufacturing firms. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation Studies*, 18(1), 19-33.
- Ajube, D., & Jeroh, E. (2023). Determinants of tax aggressiveness among non-financial listed firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, 5(7), 207-220.
- Al-Slehat, Z. A.-F. (2019). Impact of financial leverage, size and assets structure on firm value: evidence from industrial sector, Jordan. *International Business Research*, 13(1), 109-130.
- Amadi, I., & Chijioke, E. (2023). The impact of firm age on tax shield benefits in Nigerian SMEs. *International Journal of Emerging Markets and Finance*, 11(3), 232-248.
- Ayuba, S. M., & Suleiman, A. (2021). Tobin's Q and Firm Performance: Evidence from Nigerian Technology Companies. *African Journal of Business Research*, 19(1), 82–97.
- Babalola, M., & Ibrahim, J. (2023). Firm size and tax shield utilization among large Nigerian firms. *Nigerian Journal of Financial Management*, 10(1), 134-149.
- Eke, C., & Nwokolo, M. (2023). The role of economic policy changes on tax shields in Nigeria's energy sector. *African Journal of Business and Taxation*, 7(3), 156-172.
- Graham, J. R. (2000). How Big Are the Tax Benefits of Debt? *The Journal of Finance*, 55(5), 1901–1941.
- Iyefekhe, C. & Imagbe, V.U. (2019). Determinants of corporate tax avoidance: Empirical evidence of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 10(4), 173-181.
- Modigliani, F., & Miller, M. H. (1963). Corporate Income Taxes and the Cost of Capital: A Correction. *American Economic Review*, 53(3), 433–443.
- Musa, A., & Ogunbiyi, J. (2023). Capital structure decisions and tax shields in Nigerian firms. *Journal of Corporate Finance Research*, 17(2), 98-114.
- Ogbeide, I. O., Anyaduba, J. O., & Akogo, O. U. (2022). Firm Attributes and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness in Nigeria. *American Journal of Finance*, 7(2), 64–87.
- Ogunbiyi, A., & Femi, J. (2023). Impact of firm size on tax shield efficiency in Nigeria's agricultural sector. *Journal of Agricultural Finance and Management*, 10(1), 98-114.

- Okafor, E. C., & Ezeani, S. I. (2023). Return on Equity and Shareholders' Value in the Nigerian Capital Market. *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Financial Research*, 17(2), 121–134.
- Okocha, B.N & Jeroh, E. (2024). Tax shield and the value of listed non-finance entities in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Management and Commerce*, 5(1), 12-17.
- Okonkwo, I. M., Eze, R. C., & Adeyemi, O. S. (2023). Debt Tax Shield and Financial Performance: Evidence from Selected Quoted Firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 19(1), 23–41.
- Okonkwo, O.N. (2018). Determinants of taxation in Nigeria, 1980-2014. *International Journal of Research in Arts and Social Sciences*, 11(2), 20-33.
- Okoye, P., & Ihemeje, A. (2023). Comparative analysis of tax shield utilization across Nigeria's manufacturing and service sectors. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Policy*, 5(3), 99-116.
- Oyedokun, G. E., & Sorinmade, O. H. (2023). Value Added Tax, Public Revenue and Government Expenditure in Nigeria. *Indiana Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(6),4957.<https://indianapublications.com/journal/IJEBM> - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10442809>
- Oyedokun, G. E., Fowokan, E. T., Akintoye, I. R., and Dada, S. O (2018). Tax cooperative compliance and federally collected tax revenue in Nigeria. *Advance in Management*, 17(1), 193-213. A publication of the Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Ilorin, Ilorin Kwara State, Nigeria
- Oyedokun, G. E; Akintoye, I. R. & Salawu, O. R. (2018). Tax justice and federally collected tax revenue in Nigeria: A vector autoregressive approach. *Journal of Management Policy and Practice (JMPP)*. 19(4). <http://www.na-businesspress.com/jmppopen.html>
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Ayinde, O.A. (2023). Digitalization, Culture, and Taxpayers' Compliance in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 6 (12), 5888-5896. DOI: 10.47191/jefms/v6-i12-15. <https://ijefm.co.in/v6i12/15.php>
- Oyedokun, G.E., & Onigbinde, K.A. (2024). Effects of tax havens and employee tax fraud on Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting Research*, 6(1), 104–128. <https://doi.org/10.32350/jfar.61.05>
- Samuel H.U., Akpan D.C., Nsentip E.B.& Ukpe E.A. (2023) Tax Shield and Firms Value of Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 11(9), 16-34.
- Wang, Y., & Wang, Y. (2022). Profitability and Investment Behavior: Evidence from Chinese Manufacturing Firms. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Financial Studies*, 51(1), 110–128.
- Yusuf, B., & Okoh, C. (2021). Capital structure decisions in young versus mature firms: The role of tax shields. *Journal of Financial Decision-Making*, 14(2), 211-225.